

THE IMPORTANCE OF INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF MARKETS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Annotation: This article provides information on the role of markets in the field of tourism and measures taken to improve and update the infrastructure of markets in the development of tourism in our country.

Key words: Markets, supply and demand, private tourist companies, national tourist products, information.

Enter. The tourism sector is a separate segment, like any other branch of the economy in the market system. That is why it is extremely important to consider tourism activity as an interdependent system of demand and supply factors. Demand factors mainly represent international (regional) and domestic (national) tourist markets. Such markets are widely used by local residents along with foreign tourists. Supply factors include various types of activities that can attract foreign tourists (national crafts, music, and local folk customs and ceremonies).

The main part.

On December 18, 2023, under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a video selector meeting was held to discuss the issues of further expansion of production and development of services in the regions. Our country has great tourism potential. In order to use this effectively, it was emphasized that it is necessary to increase the number of hotels and guest houses.

From January 1, 2024, it was decided to prepare a master plan of historical and scenic tourism places, and to allocate additional funds for their infrastructure. Along with the repair of the streets leading to them, the task of placing trade and service stations along the roads was set. The sale of jewelry for tourists abroad is also widely established. Although there are sufficient conditions for this in our country, such products are rarely produced. Therefore, an instruction was given to organize modern jewelry complexes in each region

next year. Also, an offer was made to organize the international "Uzbekistan silk fabrics" fashion week in our country. It was noted that it is necessary to increase the convenience of our markets for tourists. It was emphasized the importance of turning them into complexes where tourists can spend days, and into a "visiting card" that reflects our culture. As a result of these measures, it was noted that more than 2 million people can be employed in the field of services and tourism.

In accordance with the President's decision, we will study the prospects of further development of Chor-su and Siyob markets, which are visited by many tourists in our country:

Known as "Chorsu" (Chor-su - "four roads" or "four ditches"), "Old Juva Market" is located in the old city at the intersection of four shopping streets, and is full of colorful wares and architecture, antiquity and folk all year round. amazes people with its culture. "Chorsu" market is one of the largest markets in Uzbekistan and Central Asia. It is located in the old part of Tashkent city called "Eski shahar", on Navoi street of Almazor district. Chorsu market was known in the Middle Ages and was of great importance on the Great Silk Road. In the central part of the bazaar ceiling, covered with decorations, there is a monumental domed structure with a diameter of about 300-350 meters - a three-story winter building of the bazaar with an elevator system. Downstairs there is a basement corridor with many rooms. Trade stalls are located on the middle and upper floors. The rows in the market are divided according to the types of goods they sell: vegetables, fruits, nuts, oriental sweets, spices, grains, and there are separate pavilions for clothes and household goods. This bazaar is of special interest because it is located in the heart of the historical-architectural complex of the XVI-XVII centuries. These are Ko'kaldosh and Khoja Ahror madrasas, Jome mosque. According to the records of travelers of the past centuries, there were countless goods, small shops, baths, caravanserais, teahouses and other establishments in the main market of Tashkent. In those days, Chorsu was a trading city. The goods in the modern Chorsu market are divided into:

- 1) products;
- 2) craft rows;
- 3) clothing market.

The first two sections are under large ball pavilions and security-style blue dome panels. In the center is the main, largest dome, reminiscent of a circus dome in size and shape. There are many fruits and vegetables and household items around. Products are also divided into sections. For example, they have a branch that only sells milk. These are mainly yogurt (sour milk, kefir), cottage cheese and cottage cheese. Cooking a famous oriental "dish". The clothing section of the market sells various European and national clothes, colorful fabrics and blankets (traditional cotton mattresses). There are a number of cafes and restaurants such as cheap market, national babo, pilaf, somsa manti, products. Chor-su lady is one of the most popular dishes.

Siyob bazaar is a bazaar in Samarkand, one of the largest and largest bazaars in Uzbekistan and Central Asia. The area of the market is more than 7 hectares. The Silver Market is one of the most visited markets in the city. The name of the market comes from the name of the Siyob river of the city.

The word "Siyob" is translated from the Persian and Tajik languages as black water, river. Siyob Bazaar is located at the intersection of Islam Karimov and Shokhi Zinda Streets, the central center of the city of Samarkand, built as the old city. 1 km south of the Siyob Bazaar is Registan Square, near the main entrance is the Bibikhanim Mosque and the mausoleum of the same name, 500 meters east of the market is the Shahi Zinda Mausoleum Ensemble and Hazrat-Khizr Mosque, Afrosiyob is 2 kilometers north. of the market. The building is under a dome and has several stalls with many shops. There are 7-storey large verandas, a row of shops and market stalls. There is a separate large building for meat and meat delivery, and a separate large stall for oriental sweets. "Chodiyona" shopping center and two-story "Siab" supermarket. There are a number of cafes and restaurants such as cheap market, national babo, pilaf, somsa manti, products. All kinds of local products, Samarkand tandirs and other products, household goods and many other products are being bought from the market. The market is famous for various meat products. You can buy your items in the market. Sales lines in the market are divided into the following according to the types of products sold in them:

household product;

- meat;
- relevant;
- fruits;
- nuts;
- oriental sweets;
- spices;
- cereals;
- no;
- cakes;
- there are stores for clothes and household goods.

In addition, the market has a series of handicrafts, where artisans make and sell certain products. Artisans can see wood carvings, copper and other metals, and carvings.

CONCLUSION

It is worth saying that the market economy, as well as tourism in other areas, should be produced by taking it as a lesson from the results achieved in the world. because we are one of the young people who are now entering the market economy, we should bring the activity of private companies to a high level in all the parts of the above classification. Because it is possible to create all conditions for the development of the tourism sector for our government. We need to further improve the infrastructure of Siyob in Upper Samarkand and Chorsu in Tashkent, provide many services for many users, provide services and improve the quality of the roadside market and our end tourists.

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